

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.10 Reports from Advisory Board and Ethics Report year 3

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Abstract

This deliverable contains the assessment, guidance, and recommendations from the members of the Advisory Board of ConcePTION on project activities and compliance of these activities with IMI regulations, ethics, and scientific standard procedures. It focuses on the progress of the project during the third year.

The feedback provided by each of the members of the Advisory board is based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the virtual General Assembly meeting of ConcePTION in April 2022. The report also contains feedback and actions points provided from the Managing Team of ConcePTION.

The members of the Advisory Board agree that ethical standards for data collection, privacy protection and human participation are met in the ConcePTION project.

Advisory Board report

The aim of this deliverable D8.10 is to report to IMI on the assessment and recommendations provided by the Advisory Board (AB) on the third year of the project. The feedback provided by each member of the Advisory board is based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the virtual General Assembly (GA) meeting of ConcePTION on April 6 and 7, 2022, as well as the project review report received from IMI. The virtual GA meeting included an overview of the achievements within ConcePTION during year three and provided the work packages with the ability to present on key topics for their work package. In addition, the communication and sustainability plans of ConcePTION were presented, as well as the importance of ConcePTION for IHI, and general feedback.

The members of the AB were invited to attend both days. They were also asked to give a 15 min presentation at the end of the GA to present their feedback. PMO contacted each member two weeks before the GA and provided questions to be answered after the GA. These questions form the structure of this deliverable and contains the recommendations and feedback provided by the AB members. Unfortunately, not all members of the AB could attend.

The questions provided to the AB are the following:

1. *What were the strengths/areas for further improvement that you have seen in the work by the WPs as it has been presented at the GAM?*
2. *What would be recommendations for the consortium going forward on the scientific content of the work?*
3. *What are some recommended strategies for regulatory engagement? (Based on IMI comment: It is imperative to begin to develop strategies about introducing policy and regulatory changes that will be driven by the new models of risk assessment.*

Regulatory change takes time, and they need to be in close contact with regulatory authorities to achieve that)

4. *What would be key considerations for the consortium to strengthen sustainability activities? (There were presentations on sustainability during the GAM and AB will be engaged once again during Y4 and Y5 specifically seeking feedback on the sustainability processes and activities)*

The members of the AB provided a report containing recommendations, guidance, and questions to the ConcePTION consortium. The report provided by the members has been collected in one single report to be submitted to IMI as deliverable D8.10.

Recommendations from the Advisory Board members

1. *What were the strengths/areas for further improvement that you have seen in the work by the WPs as it has been presented at the GAM?*

- Remark from one of the members: I see some space for improvement in the ConcePTION App: Did it work with early adapters or is there any UX research? In my opinion that is an important part of the project. I wonder, how it is assured that this will be actually used by pregnant women, since there are already many different health apps and google? Are there any ideas how to engage users with the app, that this is the pregnancy app, that informs not only, when you have doubts about medications, but in all matters concerning healthy pregnancy.

2. *What would be recommendations for the consortium going forward on the scientific content of the work?*

- The scientific content of the work, despite the pandemic, has been impressive. Continued progress on the Work Packages in all areas is encouraging.
- Additional attention to specific strategies on how to prioritize products for study in the future, for identifying and evaluating signal detection and the appropriate response will be important scientifically and to support sustainability with limited resources.
- Planning now for dissemination.

Comments on 7.3. Ethics: Ethics framework for ConcePTION as a learning healthcare system:

Remark by one of the members:

- The ConcePTION researchers focused on justifying research: solidarity – which was expressed by women participating in interviews – is the ground-value for learning health system and the thinking behind it is: a woman/pregnant human wants to participate in research because she sympathizes (solidarity) with other pregnant humans, and they have a role in the project. In this respect I was wondering, if there was anything else in the interviews or in conceptual analysis that could serve as an

important ethical guidance for the whole system, beyond solidarity and even ethical duty to contribution to general knowledge?

- Emanuel Ezekiel and Christie Grady in their paper Four Paradigms of Clinical Research and Research Oversight (2007) argue that research ethics has an evolutionary character, and we can observe an evolution of ethical paradigms that regulate clinical research: from researcher paternalism, through regulatory protectionism, participant access, to, finally, collaborative partnership. I was wondering where on this map the ConcePTION researcher would put their ethical framework for the ConcePTION as a learning health care system.
 - Another thing that in my opinion could be further developed is the communication aspect of the ConcePTION learning system. In the framework one reads: “researchers, healthcare professionals and health institutions need to create ways to communicate new information in an understandable and respectful manner to pregnant and breastfeeding people”. However, in my opinion, this element of the project could be developed and linked also with the ConcePTION App. The project has great communication specialist producing excellent materials. However, I think that communication goes beyond that and has also informal aspects, and this could be addressed. For instance, in many countries a pregnant and subsequently breastfeeding, otherwise healthy, woman enters a healthcare system, and encounters many different healthcare specialists: obstetricians, midwives, nurses, breastfeeding assistants, pediatricians. Those healthcare specialist can differ in stressing risk of certain procedures or medicines, and do not appreciate individual benefits. This is an informal aspect of communication. I do not know, how we can get rid of this informal aspect, but maybe it can be somehow addressed
- 3. What are some recommended strategies for regulatory engagement? (Based on IMI comment: It is imperative to begin to develop strategies about introducing policy and regulatory changes that will be driven by the new models of risk assessment. Regulatory change takes time, and they need to be in close contact with regulatory authorities to achieve that)**
- There was specific discussion about the design of current pharmacovigilance data collection systems that are not amenable to broad inclusion of high-quality pregnancy or lactation reports using a common data model. The re-design of the system was acknowledged to be a long process that requires regulatory commitment – but ConcePTION should be engaged in this effort now in order to have sufficient lead time to facilitate needed changes.
- 4. What would be key considerations for the consortium to strengthen sustainability activities? (There were presentations on sustainability during the GAM and AB will be engaged once again during Y4 and Y5 specifically seeking feedback on the sustainability processes and activities)**
- Remark from one of the members: In my opinion the ConcePTION app can play here an important role, as well as knowledge bank.

- As outlined, there was a focus on the value added of the work and targeted funding sources who can appreciate that value. There should be strong and early consideration for an integrated governance structure. Investigators seem to recognize that the entire effort is not one and done – this is a living, evolving set of objectives and products will need to be continuously informed and updated by advances.
- Sustainability of Knowledge Bank seems still to require some process for equitably vetting the communications – who decides what the message is to consumers, and when new data become available, who decides if the message needs to be changed and how? How are these actions aligned (if at all) with other sources of trusted information on these topics?

5. Additional comments from individual members

Matthews Mathai, MD, PhD (WHO)

Firstly, my thanks to you and your colleagues for the opportunity to participate in the GAM. It was a good learning experience. I am impressed with the work that has been done thus far and the progress made despite pandemic related restrictions. My congratulations to everyone involved in this project for the achievements.

As mentioned in my feedback from 2021, two 2 hr Zoom calls are less than ideal for people who only attend an annual meeting. In the previous GAM, I was unfamiliar with some of the acronyms used in the discussion but this time, many presenters ensured that most terms used were made clear during the presentation. I appreciated this.

I still feel that advisors who are not directly involved in the work packages should be sent pre-meeting reading to familiarise themselves with the status of project implementation and then provide more considered inputs.

I would also suggest that advisors are updated periodically through newsletters and that scientific papers arising from the project are shared with the group as and when published.

Answers to the AB and consortium action plan

Members of the Managing Team (MT) replied to the questions provided from the Advisory board as follows:

1. What were the strengths/areas for further improvement that you have seen in the work by the WPs as it has been presented at the GAM?

Comments from AB: I see some space for improvement in the ConcePTION App: Did it work with early adapters or is there any UX research? In my opinion that is an important part

of the project. I wonder, how it is assured that this will be actually used by pregnant women, since there are already many different health apps and google? Are there any ideas how to engage users with the app, that this is the pregnancy app, that informs not only, when you have doubts about medications, but in all matters concerning healthy pregnancy.

Response from MT: This comment will be conveyed to the members working on the app and will be taken into consideration. Usability / user engagement is an important consideration for app development.

2. What would be recommendations for the consortium going forward on the scientific content of the work?

Comment from AB: Additional attention to specific strategies on how to prioritize products for study in the future, for identifying and evaluating signal detection and the appropriate response will be important scientifically and to support sustainability with limited resources.

Response from MT: Thank you for this recommendation. We agree that it is very important to direct specific attention to the way in which products are prioritized for study in the future. The consortium will take this into account in the remaining two years of the project. The sustainability plan will also include a section on this point.

Comment from AB: Planning now for dissemination.

Response from MT: We agree that planning ahead for dissemination is crucial for effective communication. Therefore, the consortium already invests time into this. We are continuously working on project related publications, webinars, and newsletters. In addition, more activities will be planned in the coming year(s).

3. What are some recommended strategies for regulatory engagement?

Comment from AB: There was specific discussion about the design of current pharmacovigilance data collection systems that are not amenable to broad inclusion of high-quality pregnancy or lactation reports using a common data model. The re-design of the system was acknowledged to be a long process that requires regulatory commitment – but ConcePTION should be engaged in this effort now in order to have sufficient lead time to facilitate needed changes.

Response from MT: We thank the advisory board for this recommendation, which we will take into account in our regulatory engagement activities during the final stages of the project.

4. What would be key considerations for the consortium to strengthen sustainability activities?

Comments from AB: Sustainability of Knowledge Bank seems still to require some process for equitably vetting the communications – who decides what the message is to consumers, and when new data become available, who decides if the message needs to be changed and how? How are these actions aligned (if at all) with other sources of trusted information on these topics?

Comments from MT: We fully agree. Quality control and proper management of communication will be an important element in the operational and governance structure for the knowledge bank.

5. Additional comments

Comments from AB: To involve the SAB more when planning for meetings, as well as throughout the entire duration of the project.

Comments from MT: Thank you very much for this comment. We have decided to indeed send reading material before the GAM, which will take place in March 2023. In addition, we have informed communications to share future newsletters and publications with the SAB.